

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

Policy Brief nº 8

Recommendations from the Danish Living Lab on AMU in cows and calves from dairy herds
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This policy brief contributes to the main goal of the ROADMAP project which is to analyse the practices and decision systems of farmers, veterinarians and other professionals involved in managing the health of farmed animals, and to the specific objective of identifying levers/incentives for a more prudent use of antibiotics in livestock production

Mozambique is experiencing a strong growth of its poultry production, allowing a substantial decrease of importations. At the same time, the number of stakeholders in the veterinary drugs markets, and the consumption of antibiotics in poultry farming skyrocketed, with potential risks of antimicrobial resistance in humans, animals and the environment. The challenge for the Mozambican Government is to support the development of the national poultry value chain without compromising the public health.

This document should be of particular relevant for policymakers and politicians

OVERVIEW

In Denmark, antimicrobial use in Dairy cattle has generally decreased over the past decade, but stayed stable or increased regarding calves.

The Danish Living Lab regarding Dairy cows and calves has worked with a number of activities, from daily practice level, educational activities (e.g. farmer groups and groups for farm employees), as well as market driven initiatives towards prudent AMU, and to political and societal levels. In the process, the situation of calves from dairy herds destined for slaughter was much debated. In the spring 2022, these calves were the center of a wider stakeholder debate, where possibilities for reducing AMU were debated. Based on common explorations and debates, there is a general agreement that efforts need to be taken aiming at reducing AMU in calves. At the same time, there is an agreed recognition that many of the challenges regarding AMU in calves are structural and connected to the relatively low economic value of calves compared to the value of milk. Thus, milk is the main sales product from dairy herds and calves are in some sense treated as a residual product.

The Danish legislation regarding AMU in cattle is negotiated regularly, and the results of negotiations between multiple sector related stakeholders are formulated in a common agreement named 'The Veterinary Agreement'. In Denmark, we currently work in accordance with the framework of the third Veterinary Agreement. In spring 2023, the negotiations for the fourth Veterinary Agreement are initiated, and the Danish Cattle Living Lab has worked to develop a contribution to the Veterinary Agreement IV by developing a number of motivated suggestions to regulations on medicine use aiming at stimulating a more prudent use, based on the expertise knowledge of the Living Lab participants. This document is currently under negotiation among the Living Lab participants. It is expected that it will be submitted during April 2023.

RELATED PROJECT OUTPUTS DEVELOPED BY THE LIVING LAB REGARDING DAIRY COWS AND CALVES

- National Cattle Conference, developed material (in Danish and not online).
- Document (in Danish and not online): 'Suggestions to relevant action aiming at reducing antibiotic use in the cattle sector, and in this way contribute to reduced risk for developing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in relation to the Veterinary Agreement 4'.

RESULTS

RECOMMENDATIONS

Knowledge transfer

The Danish Living Lab on dairy cows and calves has prepared small videos and some participants started working with groups of migrant farm workers to discuss the use of antibiotics.

Dissemination Activities

The Danish Living Lab on dairy cows and calves was present and initiated dialogues at the national cattle conference.

Homogenize standards and regulations

The Danish Living Lab on dairy cows and calves worked during a one-year period to exchange and discuss their expert opinions regarding lowering AMU. Based on the participants' experiences and opinions, a number of recommendations were agreed on.

The Living Lab agreed that two parallel lines of recommendations were necessary, namely one on medication and medicine use, and one on health promotion and disease prevention, ensuring that the animals stayed disease free and were supported to overcome any challenge. Based on experience exchange with and knowledge from colleagues in the pig sector, they also analyzed and discussed the effect of the yellow-card arrangement. As a Living Lab group, they submitted a number of suggestions to the Danish legislation authorities aiming at reducing the consumption of antibiotics in the cattle sector and in this way contribute to reducing the risk of developing antimicrobial resistance.

It is powerful to let farmers tell about their best practices to minimize AMU.

Target the groups of farm employees, when disseminating knowledge.

Continue multi-stakeholder dialogues in LL to foster mutual understanding and collected action towards more prudent AMU.

When addressing issues which are general for the whole sector, we recommend to present in fora with the entire sector is represented.

Regarding medication and AMU:

Only use narrow-spectrum antibiotics.

Oral medication with antibiotics to calves should generally be avoided.

'Yellow-card arrangements' for calves are recommended.

Special efforts should target the herds with highest AMU.

Different levels of AMU to release action plans are recommended for calves in dairy herds and calves in slaughter calf herds.

Regarding preventing disease and supporting the health of cows and calves

Requirements for increased space allowance of min. 3m²/calf through legislation.

Measuring immunity of calves should be part of the standard herd advisory service.

Some participants emphasize the importance of vaccinations.

Knowledge about AMR and AMU should be disseminated at agricultural colleges.

Digital registration of AMU should be mandatory to ensure professional and homogenized data analyses to follow up on

how antibiotics are used. Some LL participants emphasise the importance of laboratory diagnostics as a tool.

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